

Defining New Item Types for a Clinical Judgment Construct

Defining the Model

TASK MODEL

Developing a Task Model

Cognitive Operation	Expected Behavior	Potential Content
Recognize Cues	●	●
Analyze Cues	●	●
Prioritize Hypotheses	●	●
Generate Solutions	●	●
Take Action	●	●
Evaluate Outcomes	●	●

Cognitive Function	Conditioning Factor(s)	Expected Behavior(s)
Recognize Cues		

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Recognize Cues	Environment Cues:	Recognize abnormal vs normal
	Patient Observation Cues:	
	Medical Record Cues:	Recognize signs and symptoms
	Time Pressure Cues:	Identify history of

Cognitive Function	Conditioning Factor(s)	Expected Behavior(s)
Recognize Cues	Environment Cues:	Recognize abnormal vs normal
	Implied labor and delivery unit	
	Patient Observation Cues:	
	active labor at 5 cm; epidural; intact membranes; BP 115/78, P 88, R 15, T 100.4° F (38.0° C)	Recognize signs and symptoms
	Medical Record Cues:	
	augmented with oxytocin; fetal heart rate tracing is normal; two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries; blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with last delivery; medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma	
	Time Pressure Cues:	Identify history of
	40 weeks gestation is in active labor	

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	Time Pressure Cues:	Identify history of
	40 weeks gestation is in active labor	two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries; blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with last delivery; medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma

Cognitive Function	Conditioning Factor(s)	Expected Behavior(s)
Analyze Cues	Requires knowledge of:	Connection between pathophysiology and client presentation:
		Use findings/observations to determine client needs:
Prioritize Hypothesis	Indicate Resources:	Prioritize (likelihood, risk, etc)
	Indicate time pressure cues:	
Generate Solutions	Requires knowledge of:	Things to address:
		Things to avoid:

Cognitive Function	Conditioning Factor(s)	Expected Behavior(s)
Take Action	Requires knowledge of and experience with:	Request:
		antibiotics; <u>CBC</u>
		Administer:
		acetaminophen
		Perform (Skill):
		Document:
Evaluate Outcomes	Requires knowledge of and experience with:	Reassess:
	maternal complications signs/symptoms infection active labor oxytocin FHR tracings post-partum hemorrhage risks	maternal temperature FHR maternal pulse

Building Items/Tasks

TASK MODEL

Approach to Content Development

- Job task analysis produced numerous CJ task statements
- Develop authentic scenarios
 - Focus on real life, high fidelity situations
- Abstract the CJ elements from the scenarios
 - Use the task model to support item development
- Have multiple external reviewers judge scenarios & item sets
 - Current practice
 - Entry-level appropriate
 - Correct key set
- Train panels to write scenarios, write items, and review scenario/items (on-going)

Example: Initial Scenario Development

Authentic Narrative

An 8-year-old client with a history of diabetes presents to the emergency room with his mother, who reports that the child has not been feeling well for the last two days. She states he has a low-grade temperature, diarrhea, and a poor appetite. Today, the child reports he is feeling dizzy and that his head hurts. The mother also reports that he is refusing to eat or drink anything. Client vital signs upon arrival are pulse–162 beats/minute, respirations–26 breaths/minute, blood pressure–78/42 mmHg, temperature-100.3° F orally and blood serum glucose-75mg/dL. The client is admitted to the hospital, and an intravenous line is placed with 0.9% normal saline infusing at 50mL/hr. The nurse notes that the child is responsive to questions but appears lethargic. The mucous membranes appear dry, extremities are cool, and capillary refill is 3-4 seconds.

The nurse re-evaluates the client after two hours from the initial admission. The child is awake and talking, extremities remain cool, and capillary refill is 2-3 seconds. The client is asking to drink something. Client vital signs are pulse–152 beats/minute, respirations–22 breaths/minute, blood pressure–82/46 mmHg, temperature-100.2° F orally. Laboratory values: electrolytes, within normal limits; blood serum glucose, 80mg/dL.

Example:

Abstract Task Model Variables

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Example: Fill Out Task Model

Cognitive Operation	Factor Conditioning	Expected Behavior
Recognize Cues	Environmental Cues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Set <i>location</i> to <i>emergency room</i> ▪ Show <i>the presence of parent</i> Client Observation Cues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Show <i>age</i> to <i>8-10</i> ▪ Show <i>dehydration symptoms</i> (e.g., dry mucous membranes appear, cool extremities, cap refill 3-4 seconds) ▪ Show/Imply <i>lethargy</i> Medical Record Cues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Show <i>dehydration symptoms</i> (e.g., a lower-grade temperature, diarrhea, a poor appetite) ▪ Show/Imply <i>history of diabetes</i> ▪ Show/Imply <i>vital signs</i> Time Pressure Cue: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Set <i>time pressure</i> to <i>varying with onset of symptoms and current lethargy</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognize <i>abnormal vital signs</i> ▪ Recognize <i>symptoms of dehydration</i> ▪ Identify <i>the history of diabetes</i> ▪ Hypothesize <i>dehydration</i> ▪ Hypothesize <i>diabetes</i>
Analyze Cues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Require <i>knowledge of dehydration symptoms</i> ▪ Require <i>knowledge of diabetes symptoms</i> 	
Prioritize Hypotheses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Give <i>vital sign monitors</i> as <i>resources</i> ▪ Set <i>time pressure</i> to <i>vary with vital signs</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prioritize <i>dehydration</i> ▪ Address <i>dehydration</i> ▪ Avoid <i>glucose</i>
Generate Solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Require <i>knowledge of dehydration treatment and intervention</i> ▪ Require <i>knowledge of diabetes treatment and intervention</i> 	
Evaluate Outcomes	Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Require <i>experience of administering isotonic fluid</i> Client Observation Cue: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Show <i>client awaking and talking</i> ▪ Imply <Set <i>vital signs</i> to <i>varying with action</i>> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Check <i>vital signs</i> ▪ Check <i>lethargy</i>

Designing New Item & Response Types

- SMEs identified item & response types to measure CJ elements
 - Worked with an application developer to render different item types
 - Worked with psychometrics to clarify scoring rules
 - Iterative approach:
 - Create → Render → Evaluate → Refactor → Evaluate
- Goals:
 - Develop item/response types that assess the CJ elements
 - Provide initial proof of concept – Initial evaluation of validity
 - Utilized a continual, on-going learning method
 - Provide continual feedback on item designs, content issues and item coding clarification

Developing the Tasks/Items to Measure the Construct

ITEM DEVELOPMENT

Extended Multiple Response: Evaluating treatment for a client

- Rationale:
 - Specify whether new findings indicate an improvement, a worsening condition, or are unrelated
- CJ element: Analyze Cues
- Other uses:
 - Prioritizing (actions to take, pick most and least important)
 - Generating solutions (actions to take, buttons for Important to do, OK to do, Should not do)

The nurse is caring for a client who has pneumonia. Findings upon admission:

Medical history	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
Vital signs	Blood pressure 122/84 Pulse 118 Respirations 28 Oral temperature 101.9° F Oxygen saturation 94% on oxygen at 2 L/min via nasal cannula
Physical examination	Respiratory: frequent, nonproductive cough; thick, purulent sputum obtained by suction; wheezes bilaterally on inspiration and expiration, crackles bilaterally in posterior bases; shortness of breath with exertion
Labs	ABG: pH 7.38, PaCO ₂ 50, HCO ₃ 23, PaO ₂ 78 Sputum culture pending

The nurse is assessing the client 24 hours after admission and initiation of treatment. Specify how the nurse should interpret each finding by clicking the button for Unrelated to diagnosis, Sign of potential improvement, or Sign of potentially worsening condition.

Finding	Unrelated to diagnosis	Sign of potential improvement	Sign of potentially worsening condition
Digital clubbing	⊗	○	○
Oxygen saturation 93% on room air	○	⊗	○
ABG pH 7.31	○	○	○
Frequent, productive cough	○	○	○
Shortness of breath at rest	○	○	○
Increased anteroposterior chest diameter	○	○	○

Drag-n-Drop: Rank Risk Factors

- Rationale:
 - Review information about clients to determine which is at the highest risk for different types of cancer
- CJ Element: Prioritize Hypotheses
- Other uses:
 - Analyze cues
 - Generate hypotheses
 - Evaluate outcomes

The nurse is screening female clients at an outpatient clinic. Specify which of the clients is at highest risk of developing cervical cancer, which is at highest risk of developing ovarian cancer, and which is at highest risk of developing breast cancer by dragging the client description to the appropriate box on the right.

Clients:

- 59-year-old client who
 - had first sexual activity at 15 years of age
 - has had approximately 11 sexual partners
 - has had 3 full-term pregnancies, first at age 18
 - smokes cigarettes
 - has a sister with breast cancer
- 58-year-old client who
 - has a sister with ovarian cancer
 - has had approximately 6 sexual partners
 - experienced menopause at 56 years of age
 - has had no pregnancies
- 62-year-old client who
 - had ovarian cancer and is in remission
 - had menarche at 11 years of age
 - had one full-term pregnancy at 35 years of age
 - has a body mass index of 32
- 60-year-old client who
 - has had 4 full-term pregnancies, first at 21 years of age
 - breast-fed her children for the first 8-10 months
 - used oral contraceptives for 8 years
 - smokes cigarettes

Drag and drop

Client at highest risk for cervical cancer:

Client at highest risk for breast cancer:

Client at highest risk for ovarian cancer:

Evaluating Trends

The nurse is caring for a client with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease who was admitted 4 days ago for treatment for bacterial pneumonia. The nurse has received a prescription to discharge the client, who is to continue antibiotic therapy at home and have a follow-up office visit in 4 days. The nurse reviews the following information for the client:

Client Information					
	Office visit 2 months ago	Upon admission 4 days ago	2 days ago	Yesterday	Today
Oxygen saturation	88% on room air, 91% on 2 L/min by nasal cannula	80% on 2 L/min by nasal cannula, 92% on 6 L/min by face mask	93% on 2 L/min by nasal cannula	93% on 2 L/min by nasal cannula	87% on room air, 92% on 2 L/min by nasal cannula
Arterial blood gases:					
PaO₂	80	65	70	75	80
PaCO₂	44	53	50	49	45
HCO₃	29	36	34	29	27
pH	7.35	7.28	7.30	7.33	7.36
White blood cell count		14,300/mm ³ (14.3 x 10 ⁹)	13,920/mm ³ (13.9 x 10 ⁹)	13,100/mm ³ (13.1 x 10 ⁹)	12,600/mm ³ (12.6 x 10 ⁹)
Hemoglobin		18.8 g/dL (188 g/L)	18.7 g/dL (187 g/L)	18.8 g/dL (18.8 g/L)	18.8 g/dL (188 g/L)

- Considering only these findings, is it safe for the nurse to discharge the client?
 - Yes, the nurse should continue to plan for discharge.
 - No, the nurse should discuss the findings with the client's primary health care provider and ask to postpone discharge.

- Click to highlight the three findings that provide the strongest support for your decision.

Scenario: Static

Case Study Screen 1 of 4

The nurse is assessing a client who has a Clostridium Difficile infection.

The nurse finds the following:

Physical Exam

	Findings
Gastrointestinal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• abdomen soft and nontender• bowel sounds active x 4
Cardiovascular	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• weak, irregular pulse
Respiratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• crackles in middle and lower lobes of lungs
Integumentary	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• skin elastic with normal turgor• moist mucous membranes• nonpitting bilateral pedal edema
Musculoskeletal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• report of fatigue• report of leg cramps• difficulty rising to go to the bathroom, saying "my legs feel weak"
Neurologic	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• oriented to person, place and time• lethargic• pupils equal and reactive to light• weak patellar reflex

➤ Complete the following sentence:

The nurse should recognize that this combination of findings is indicative of

➤ Highlight the finding(s) at left that support the choice you made above.

Case Study Screen 2 of 4

The nurse is assessing a client who has a Clostridium Difficile infection.

The nurse reviews the following Medical History information in the client's medical record:

Physical
Exam

Medical
History

- 66 years old
- Male
- Allergic to penicillin
- Hyperlipidemia diagnosed approximately 8 years ago, managed with gemfibrozil
- Hypertension diagnosed approximately 6 years ago, managed with lisinopril
- Heart failure diagnosed 4 years ago, managed with hydrochlorothiazide
- Osteoarthritis of bilateral knees and wrists, pain managed with acetaminophen
- Clostridium difficile infection diagnosed 2 days ago, frequent diarrheal stools for past 4 days

- Click to highlight the factor(s) in the client's medical history that increase the client's risk for developing the potential problem you identified based on the physical exam.

Case Study Screen 3 of 4

The nurse is assessing a client who has a Clostridium Difficile infection.

The nurse receives and reviews the following following laboratory test results:

Physical Exam	Medical History	Laboratory Test Results																								
		<table border="1"><thead><tr><th>Laboratory Test</th><th>Result</th><th>Reference Range</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>serum sodium</td><td>142 mEq/L (142 mmol/L)</td><td>136-145 mEq/L (136-145 mmol/L)</td></tr><tr><td>serum potassium</td><td>3.1 mEq/L (3.1 mmol/L)</td><td>3.5-5.0 mEq/L (3.5-5.0 mmol/L)</td></tr><tr><td>serum calcium</td><td>10.0 mg/dL (2.5 mmol/L)</td><td>9.0-10.5 mg/dL (2.25-2.62 mmol/L)</td></tr><tr><td>serum magnesium</td><td>1.7 mEq/L (0.85 mmol/L)</td><td>1.3-2.1 mEq/L (0.65-1.05 mmol/L)</td></tr><tr><td>blood urea nitrogen</td><td>15 mg/dL (5.4 mmol/L)</td><td>10-20 mg/dL (3.6-7.1 mmol/L)</td></tr><tr><td>serum creatinine</td><td>0.9 mg/dL (79.6 µmol/L)</td><td>0.6-1.2 mg/dL (53-106 µmol/L)</td></tr><tr><td>urine specific gravity</td><td>1.020</td><td>1.005-1.030</td></tr></tbody></table>	Laboratory Test	Result	Reference Range	serum sodium	142 mEq/L (142 mmol/L)	136-145 mEq/L (136-145 mmol/L)	serum potassium	3.1 mEq/L (3.1 mmol/L)	3.5-5.0 mEq/L (3.5-5.0 mmol/L)	serum calcium	10.0 mg/dL (2.5 mmol/L)	9.0-10.5 mg/dL (2.25-2.62 mmol/L)	serum magnesium	1.7 mEq/L (0.85 mmol/L)	1.3-2.1 mEq/L (0.65-1.05 mmol/L)	blood urea nitrogen	15 mg/dL (5.4 mmol/L)	10-20 mg/dL (3.6-7.1 mmol/L)	serum creatinine	0.9 mg/dL (79.6 µmol/L)	0.6-1.2 mg/dL (53-106 µmol/L)	urine specific gravity	1.020	1.005-1.030
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- For each potential action listed below, click to specify whether the action is
- indicated for the client given the findings,
 - non-essential but not harmful to the client, or
 - contraindicated for the client.

Potential action	Indicated	Non-essential	Contraindicated
Monitor the client for circumoral paresthesia.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Initiate seizure precautions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Withhold the next dose of lisinopril.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Withhold the next dose of hydrochlorothiazide.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Request a prescription to apply a cardiac monitor.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Request a prescription to administer an intravenous bolus of potassium.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Encourage the client to eat oranges, potatoes, and low-fat yogurt.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Case Study Screen 4 of 4

The nurse is assessing a client who has a Clostridium Difficile infection.

The nurse has applied a continuous cardiac monitor and observes the following cardiac rhythm:

➤ The electrocardiogram strip at left demonstrates which of the following cardiac rhythms?

- normal sinus rhythm with premature ventricular contractions
- normal sinus rhythm
- atrial flutter
- tachycardia

➤ The nurse should continue to monitor the client's cardiac rhythm because the client is at increased risk for developing which of the following?

- prolonged PR interval
- tall, tented T wave
- presence of a U wave
- ST segment elevation

➤ Complete the two sentences below by dragging from the Causes box.

The manifestation of decreased cardiac output is caused by

The manifestation of muscle weakness and leg cramps is caused by

Causes

a shift of water from extracellular fluid into intracellular space

increased neuromuscular irritability

decreased contractility of cardiac muscle

decreased resting membrane potential of skeletal muscle cells

Scenario: Evolving

Case Study Screen 1 of 3

The healthcare team is caring for a 64-year-old male client who has been receiving chemotherapy for lung cancer. The client's last chemotherapy administration was 7 days ago.

Office visit, at 0900

The client visits the oncology clinic for routine follow-up care. While assessing the client, the nurse notes the following:

- Vital signs: blood pressure 104/80, heart rate 110, temperature 101.8° F (38.8° C), respiratory rate 22, oxygen saturation 98% on room air
- Lung sounds diminished on right posterior middle lobe, which is consistent with lung lesions
- Periodic dry cough
- Client report of chills, nausea, weakness, and a feeling of malaise
- Redness and tenderness at peripherally inserted central catheter (PICC) site

The nurse takes the following actions:

- Assesses the client's mental status
- Notifies the primary health care provider of the findings
- Requests an order for a complete blood cell count

➤ Were the nurse's actions appropriate?

- All of the nurse's actions were appropriate.
- Some of the nurse's actions were not appropriate.

Case Study Screen 2 of 3

The healthcare team is caring for a 64-year-old male client who has been receiving chemotherapy for lung cancer. The client's last chemotherapy administration was 7 days ago.

Office visit, at 0900

Hospital admission,
at 1030

The client is admitted to an inpatient oncology unit for further evaluation and treatment. The admitting nurse notes the following:

- Vital signs: blood pressure 100/78, heart rate 114, temperature 101.7° F (38.7° C), respiratory rate 22, oxygen saturation 97% on room air
- Pulse thready
- Respirations deep, lung sounds diminished on right posterior middle lobe, periodic dry cough
- Hypoactive bowel sounds
- Skin pale, warm and dry
- Mental status: alert and oriented x 3

➤ The nurse should anticipate receiving orders for which of the following? Select all that apply.

- Serum lactate
- Clear liquid diet
- Intravenous fluids
- Intravenous antibiotics
- Continuous cardiac monitoring
- Blood culture from the PICC line
- Blood culture from a peripheral venipuncture
- Complete blood cell count with differential
- Assignment to a room with positive air pressure

Case Study Screen 3 of 3

The healthcare team is caring for a 64-year-old male client who has been receiving chemotherapy for lung cancer. The client's last chemotherapy administration was 7 days ago.

Office visit, at 0900

Hospital admission,
at 1030

6 hours later, at 1630

Six hours after admission, the laboratory test results are as follows:

Complete blood cell count:

Hemoglobin 16.1 g/dL (161 g/L)

Hematocrit 42% (0.42)

Total white blood cell count 13,200/mm³ (13.2 x 10⁹/L)

Platelet count 155,000/mm³ (155 x 10⁹/L)

Blood cultures x 2: results pending

The client's PICC line has been removed. The nurse has inserted a 14-gauge peripheral venous access device. The client's primary health care provider ordered imipenem/cilastatin, and the client received the first dose 5 hours ago.

The nurse is assessing the client and notes the following:

- Vital signs: blood pressure 98/74, heart rate 120, temperature 101.7° F (38.7° C), respiratory rate 24, oxygen saturation 97% on room air
- Deep respirations, moist crackles in lung bases
- Pulse thready, capillary refill 1 second
- Skin pale and cool
- Urine output 26 ml/hr
- Client restless, alert to person and place but not to time
- T-wave inversion in cardiac rhythm

➤ Which of the following actions should the nurse take? Select all that apply.

- Administer supplemental oxygen.
- Place the client in a Fowler's position.
- Anticipate orders to administer intravenous crystalloids.
- Call for the facility's emergency response team.
- Bring the unit's crash cart into the client's room.
- Monitor the client's vital signs a minimum of every 30 minutes.

Scenario: Evolving

Case Study Screen 4 of 5

The nurse is caring for an 8-year-old client who experienced a cervical spinal cord injury four days ago and is receiving mechanical ventilation.

Progress Notes

- 1410** The client received a nebulized bronchodilator treatment followed by chest physiotherapy and suctioning 15 minutes ago.
- 1420** The high pressure alarm on the ventilator has begun to sound. The client is agitated and appears to be trying to cough.
- 1440** Clear thick yellow secretions were suctioned from the client's endotracheal tube. The client's oxygen saturation is 88% even though the client is being hyperventilated with 100% oxygen. The high pressure alarm continues to sound and the client remains agitated. Breath sounds are decreased in the right lower lobe. The endotracheal tube is appropriately positioned and securely taped. The client's lips are moist and the skin is warm. Both radial and pedal pulses are palpable. The client's hand grasps are strong.

- Click to highlight the findings at 1440 that would be important for the nurse to follow up.